

reacting α -formyl-naphthalene with malonic acid, had m.p. 212°. Its ethyl ester, m.p. 37°, on bromination gave the corresponding dibromo-derivative, m.p. 70°. The latter was converted by literature methods⁹ to α -naphthylpropionic acid, m.p. 135°. Its ethyl ester had b.p. 120/0.2 mm; ν_{max} 2 220 (C=C) and 1 700 cm^{-1} (CO); δ 1.38 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 4.35 (2H, q, OCH_2Me) and 7.5 (7H, m, ArH).

Condensation of arylacetamides with ethyl α -naphthylpropionate: Arylacetamide (0.0172 mol) and powdered sodium (0.0172 g-atom) in dry benzene (150 ml) was kept under reflux for 20 h. α -Naphthylpropionic ester (0.0172 mol) was then added, and heated under reflux for further 3 h. The mixture was then poured into ice-cold water (150 ml) and the benzene layer separated. The alkaline aqueous layer was acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract shaken with sodium hydrogen carbonate solution. The non-acidic ethereal and benzene extracts were combined, dried and evaporated. The residual solid was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 30–40°) to give 1 as pale yellow needles (Table 1). The sodium hydrogen carbonate washings after acidification, extraction with ether and evaporation gave a solid, which was mainly α -naphthylpropionic acid, m.p. 135°.

Condensation of ethyl α -naphthylpropionate with benzyl cyanide, ethyl phenylacetate and N-acetylindole: The condensations were carried out as described for the analogous condensation of ethyl phenylpropionate with the above nucleophiles^{4,5,7,8}. The physical data of the products are as follows: 2 (35%), m.p. 202°; ν_{max} 3 500–3 000 (OH) and 2 220 cm^{-1} (C=C and N=N); δ 7.5–8.0 (m); 3 (15%), m.p. 75°; ν_{max} 3 500 (OH) and 2 230 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 2.2 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH_2Me) and 7.6–8.0 (13H, m, ArH+OH); 4 (45%), m.p. 45°; ν_{max} 3 500–3 200 (OH), 2 230 (C=C), 1 700 and 1 670 cm^{-1} (CO); δ 6.3 (1H, s, C(OH)=CH-CO), 6.6 (1H, d, indole 3-H), 7.5–8.0 (12H, m, other ArH) and 11.0 (1H, s, exchangeable enolic OH).

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Action of Grignard Reagents on 8-Bromo-3(*H*)-oxonaphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran Derivatives

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SEVERAL studies¹⁻⁷ are already being reported on reactions between Grignard reagents and coumarins having an ethyl ester function. In the present investigation, ethyl 8-bromo-3(*H*)-oxonaphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran-2-carboxylate (1a)⁸ and the corresponding carboxamide (1b)⁸ were treated with various Grignard reagents.

Thus, excess phenylmagnesium bromide reacted with 1a to furnish only one isolable product which gave a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. This together with analytical and spectroscopic data (Table 1) led to the formulation of this product as 1,1,3-triphenyl-2-benzoyl-3-(6-bromo-2-hydroxy-1-naphthyl)propene-1 (2). However, reaction of 1b with excess phenylmagnesium bromide under reflux for 3 h furnished 8-bromo-1,3-diphenyl-1',2'-dihydro-3-hydroxy-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran-2-*N*-phenylcarboxamide (3) as the only isolable product. It seems that the reaction in this case involves 1,2-addition to the carbonyl group of pyran moiety of 1b along with 1,4-addition. The interaction of 1a with excess alkylmagnesium halides affords ethyl 1-alkyl-8-bromo-1,2-dihydro-3(*H*)-oxonaphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran-2-carboxylates (4a-c), while 1b furnished 1-alkyl-8-bromo-1,2-dihydro-3(*H*)-oxonaphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran-2-*N*-phenylcarboxamides (4d-f). Evidently compounds 4 were produced as a result of the 1,4-addition of the alkylmagnesium halides. These results are in full agreement with that obtained by Abou-Assali *et al.*⁹ for coumarin itself.

1a; R = CO_2Et
1b; R = CONHPh

2

3

- 4a; R = CO₂Et, R¹ = Me
 4b; R = CO₂Et, R¹ = Et
 4c; R = CO₂Et, R¹ = n-Bu
 4d; R = CONHPh, R¹ = Me
 4e; R = CONHPh, R¹ = Et
 4f; R = CONHPh, R¹ = n-Bu

under reduced pressure and the residual oil after trituration several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) gave a solid which on recrystallisation from benzene furnished 2 and 3 (Table 1).

Action of alkylmagnesium halides on 1: Compound 1 (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) was treated as above with a solution of alkylmagnesium bromide (0.06 mol) in dry ether (50 ml) to produce 4a–f (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula (M ⁺ , m/z)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			ν _{max} cm ⁻¹	δ
				C	H	N		
2	228	50	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Br (595)	76.45 (76.64)	4.40 (4.45)	—	3 100 (OH), 1 600, 1 640 (CO)	6.4 (1H, s, CH), 10.65 (1H, s, OH obscured by D ₂ O), (7.0–7.9) (25H, m, ArH)
3	150	40	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ NBr	69.60 (69.82)	4.30 (4.36)	2.40 (2.55)	3 500, 3 320 (OH, NH), 1 740 (CO)	
4a	235 ^a	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₄ Br	55.95 (56.20)	4.00 (4.13)	—	2 960 (aliph CH), 1 660, 1 635 (CO), 1 230, 1 270 (CO.O.CO)	
4b	255 ^a	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₄ Br	57.00 (57.29)	4.40 (4.51)	—	—	
4c	225 ^b	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ Br	58.85 (59.26)	5.10 (5.19)	—	—	
4d	155 ^a	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₃ NBr	61.40 (61.61)	3.55 (3.67)	3.30 (3.42)	3 300 (NH), 2 920 (aliph CH), 1 650, 1 760 (CO), 1 160, 1 230 (CO.O.CO)	
4e	135 ^a	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ NBr	62.20 (62.41)	3.85 (4.02)	3.10 (3.31)	—	
4f	146 ^a	55	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₃ NBr	63.50 (63.72)	4.80 (4.87)	2.90 (3.10)	—	

^aethanol, ^bbenzene

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckmann Accu Lab 4 instrument, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a EM 360/390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a MAT 112 instrument. Analytical data were determined in the Microanalytical Unit, Cairo University.

Action of phenylmagnesium bromide on 1: A solution of phenylmagnesium bromide (0.06 mol) in dry ether (50 ml) was added in one lot to a solution of 1 (0.02 mol) in dry benzene (100 ml). The mixture was gently warmed on a water-bath for 3 h and poured dropwise with vigorous stirring into ice-cold 10% H₂SO₄. The organic layer was then separated, dried (Na₂SO₄), solvent removed

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